

HIGH TEMPERATURE EFFECTS ON THE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF GLASS FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The influence of elevated temperatures on the static compressive behaviour of unidirectional glass/polypropylene (ICI Plytron) laminates is examined. Tests are conducted between 21°C and 120°C to provide variation in the constitutive behaviour of the polymer matrix and thus additional variation in the support provided to the glass fibres. It is found that the laminate loses strength as the operating temperature increases and failure occurs due to fibre microbuckling. At about 50°C the failure mode switches from in-plane to out-of-plane microbuckling. As the test temperature increases the shear strength/stiffness of the resin is considerably reduced; this decreases the amount of side support for the fibres and reduces the strain level at which fibre buckling initiates. Growth of this damage requires little additional load, suggesting that compression strength is controlled by initiation, rather than propagation of microbuckling. Fracture characteristics are identified using optical and scanning electron microscopy. Theoretical models are employed to predict damage.

Keywords: Compression, ICI Plytron, Composite laminates, Fibre microbuckling, High temperature, Fracture analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Continuous fibre-reinforced plastics are being used in an ever increasing number of structural applications. However, more efficient use of these materials is limited by their apparent low compressive strength especially under hot-wet conditions. Most composite laminates based on carbon and glass fibres, and polymeric resins are weaker in compression than in tension due to fibre microbuckling [1-3]. This is an instability failure mode which nucleates locally (e.g. free-edge, voids, resin rich regions) and propagates under little additional load through the laminate, causing a narrow zone within the 0° plies to lose structural integrity, Figure 1.

From theoretical developments on the compressive strength of unidirectional laminates [4-9] it is suggested that failure induced by fibre microbuckling is dependent on the shear strength/modulus of the matrix (resin) material. To assess the validity of these models the present study investigates the effect of resin ductility (varied as a function of the test temperature) on the compressive strength of unidirectional glass/polypropylene (glass/pp) laminates. Failure mechanisms are examined and strength measurements are compared with theoretical predictions.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Manufacture of glass/pp laminates

The material selected for this study consists of continuous glass fibres in a thermoplastic matrix of polypropylene (65 vol% resin content). It comes under the ICI (Imperial Chemical Industries) trade name 'Plytron' and is produced in 240mm wide prepreg for laminate assembly. An elevated temperature compression moulding technique was employed to manufacture $[0_4]_S$ and $[(\pm 45)_2]_S$ glass/pp laminates. Sheets of the prepreg material were cut to 260mm by 240mm using a guillotine and laid together by hand. Eight plies were used in the composite plates which resulted in a cured laminate thickness of approximately 3.8mm. Teflon coated porous bleed fabric and absorbent cloth were used to sandwich the laminate during compression moulding which resulted in the removal of excess polymer matrix. The manufacturer's standard compression moulding cycle was followed which produced laminates of acceptable quality. There was no visual evidence of any voids or porosity and the surface of the composite plates were flat and smooth. Sectioning and optical microscopy studies revealed that the void content was less than 2% and some fibre misalignment in the $[0_4]_S$ laminates was evident. Initial fibre imperfections in compression testing reduce the laminate strength [3] and therefore extra care must be taken during the moulding process.

2.2 Specimen design and mechanical tests

Unidirectional fibre-reinforced composites are highly anisotropic materials and premature failure due to Poisson deformation (brooming) may occur when axial compression is applied. This failure occurs on the load bearing surfaces and is characterised by extensive longitudinal splitting and lateral movement of material at the specimen ends. In the present investigation the modified Celanese method [10] was used to evaluate the compressive properties of the unidirectional glass/pp laminates. This test method employs tabbed specimen ends that are shear loaded, thereby eliminating the primary source of brooming. The specimens tested had a gauge length of 13mm which is a compromise between the requirement to eliminate Euler bending and the need to avoid end effects, while providing adequate space for strain gauges. The specimen width and thickness were 10mm and 3.8mm, respectively.

The compressive tests were performed on a screw-driven machine of capacity 10kN at a crosshead displacement of 0.017mms^{-1} . To measure the compressive strength of the laminates as a function of temperature the Celanese rig was adapted to hot air heating. Two extra inspection ports were drilled on the Celanese alignment sleeve and a hot air blower was attached. Symmetric airflow was achieved and the specimen was heated evenly. The temperature of the specimen was monitored by a thermocouple. It took approximately 5 minutes to reach 120°C and the specimens were allowed to 'soak' at temperature for 10-15 minutes before being tested. Using this apparatus tests were carried out at room temperature (21°C), 50°C , 80°C , 100°C and 120°C . Shear strength properties were obtained by testing $[(\pm 45)_2]_S$ laminates in tension at elevated temperature. Mechanical tests were conducted following the procedures outlined in CRAG test methods [10]. Longitudinal and transverse strains for tension and compression were measured by 1mm long foil strain gauges that retained accuracy over the range of temperatures used in this study.

3. TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental results consist of stress-strain plots, fracture stresses and strains, photographs showing the overall failure mode of selected failed specimens and optical and scanning electron micrographs of fracture surfaces. The tensile properties of the glass/pp system are not discussed in detail but presented in Tables 1 for comparison purposes; at least four specimens were tested at each temperature level.

3.1 Stress-strain data

Compressive failure in all specimens is catastrophic and quite localised, Figure 2. A kink band structure (fibre microbuckling) occurs without warning and immediately leads to laminate

breakage. Fracture is within the specimen gauge length implying that the test is successful. A plot of the applied axial stress as a function of average axial strain measured by back-to-back strain gauges is

Table 1. Tensile strength properties of glass/polypropylene laminates at various test temperatures

Property	Temperature °C				
	21	50	80	100	120
0° Tension					
Strength (MPa)	550	470	411	350	280
Modulus (GPa)	32.5	27.6	25.3	23.4	20.1
Strain to failure %	1.92	1.8	1.72	1.6	1.4
90° Tension					
Strength (MPa)	11	7	5	4	-
Modulus (GPa)	4.1	2.4	1.5	1.4	-
Strain to failure %	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9	-
± 45° Tension					
Shear strength (MPa)	55	45	38	32	27
Shear modulus (GPa)	2.1	1.3	0.8	0.5	0.3
Shear strain to failure %	19.5	26	32	39	45

shown in Figure 3, for two typical specimens tested at room temperature. The mean compressive strength is 317MPa, which is less than 60% of the tensile strength. The average failure strain and the Young's modulus (measured at 0.25% applied strain) are 0.98% and 29.5GPa, respectively. The effect of temperature on compressive properties of the unidirectional laminate can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Compressive strength properties of unidirectional glass/pp laminates as a function of temperature.

Property	Temperature °C				
	21	50	80	100	120
0° Compression					
Strength (MPa)	317	234	178	149	108
Modulus (GPa)	29.5	26.4	23.5	22	20
Strain to failure %	0.98	0.85	0.68	0.54	0.47

The values quoted in Table 2 are based on the average of four specimens tested at each temperature level. The results demonstrate that temperature has a marked influence on the compressive strength. At operating temperature of 120°C the strength has been reduced by more than 60% and the failure strain has dropped by approximately 50%. This is because the modulus of the matrix is reduced substantially with increasing temperature, Table 1. In uniaxial compression reduction in matrix modulus means reduced side support for the fibres which promotes premature failure of the composite by fibre microbuckling. The results in Tables 1 and 2 suggest that the compressive strength is more temperature dependent than the tensile strength. In general, the tensile strength of a composite depends more on its fibre reinforcement, but compressive strength relies more upon its matrix material.

3.2 Compression fracture modes

Damage to the room temperature unidirectional specimens involves fibre movement in the plane of the laminate (in-plane fibre micro-buckling) along a 20°-25° line from the transverse axis, Figure 4. In Figure 4 the optical micrograph shows that the fibres break at two points, which create a band

inclined at $\beta \approx 25^\circ$ to the horizontal axis (or 65° to the fibre axis). It was observed in all specimens that angle β remains constant. The microbuckle once started from the free edge or a pre-existing material imperfection, such as voids, resin rich regions and fibre misalignment, keeps its orientation and propagation. Berg and Salama [11] argued that the kink band must be inclined in order to permit the buckled fibres to undergo both compressive and shear deformation. The reason is that microbuckling along planes, which permit shear displacement as buckling proceeds requires smaller compressive stress than does buckling on a plane that does not permit shear displacement. (i.e. planes perpendicular to the fibre axis.) The broken fibre segments in Figure 4 are approximately 25-30 fibre diameters long and have rotated by almost 30° from the loading axis ($\phi = 30^\circ$). Once failure has occurred, the kink inclination angle ϕ can increase rapidly if the load is not immediately removed. These values are similar to those reported by Hahn [12] for S-glass/epoxy composite. For a carbon fibre-epoxy system examined in [3], β was found equal to 5° - 15° , $\phi = 30^\circ$ and $w=8$ -10 fibre diameters. Whether the angle of kink band inclination and the kink band width are of significance is still unclear. A scanning electron micrograph of the fracture surface of a selected specimen is shown in Figure 5. It exhibits well defined steps and it is evident from Figure 5b that each fibre fails in bending.

In the case of specimens tested at temperatures higher than 50°C damage was confined to out-of-plane deformation in an almost 90° kink band across the specimen width. The kink band width measured 35-40 fibre diameters. Failed specimens show features quite distinct from those observed in specimens in which fibre buckling occurred in-plane, Figure 6. The strain level at which out-of-plane microbuckling initiates is reduced with increasing temperature and at 120°C is less than 50% of the strain required to initiate in-plane microbuckling. Thus the out-of-plane microbuckling has been precipitated by a weaker ply interface in the hot specimen due to a reduction of fibre/matrix bond. Clearly, any weakening of the matrix or fibre/matrix interface arising from elevated temperature increases the probability of out-of-plane buckling of the fibres

4. STRENGTH PREDICTIONS

A number of theories for the compressive strength of unidirectional composite laminates have been proposed and these have been reviewed by Stuart [13], Hahn [12], Haeberle *et al.* [14] and Soutis [3]. In the present section we apply Rosen's [4] and more recently developed Budiansky's [8] model to predict the strength of the glass/pp system. The classic study of Rosen [4] is based on buckling theory for bars on an elastic foundation and suggests that the compressive strength σ_c is only dependent on the (initial) matrix shear modulus G_m and the fibre volume fraction V_f :

$$\sigma_c = \frac{G_m}{1 - V_f} \approx G_c \quad (1)$$

where G_c is the composite shear modulus. For the glass/pp laminates Equation 1 is found to significantly overestimate the compressive strength for all temperature levels. More detailed investigations, for instance incorporating a three-dimensional continuum rather than treating matrix and fibre as two-dimensional plates [5] produced similar results. This suggests that microbuckling is a plastic rather than an elastic event. Results presented in Tables 1 and 2 indicate that the compressive strength of pytron is only 20-25% of the shear modulus.

Argon [6] and Budiansky [8] identified the shear yield strength of the composite τ_y and the initial misalignment angle $\bar{\phi}$ of the fibres as the main factors governing the compressive strength. For a rigid perfectly plastic matrix material, Budiansky found that the compressive strength σ_c is given by

$$\sigma_c = \frac{\tau_y}{\bar{\phi}} \quad (2)$$

where τ_y is a matrix dominated property. In Figure 7 the compressive strength of the glass/pp laminates predicted by Equation 2 is plotted versus test temperature T; the τ_y is taken as half the value of the shear strength τ_f , Table 1, and $\bar{\phi}$ is taking values between 4° and 7° . We have observed such fibre imperfections in section studies for the glass/pp laminates. It can be seen that for $\bar{\phi} \approx 6^\circ$ the agreement between theoretical and experimental results is acceptable.

Budiansky's analysis predicts correctly that shear strength and fibre imperfection are important parameters affecting the compressive strength σ_c of the composite. However, it is not possible to say exactly how σ_c will vary with fibre content, which makes verification of Equation 2 difficult. Also the value of $\bar{\phi}$ may be quite arbitrary and as such the results of Equation 2 may be unreliable.

Recently, Steif[9] has modelled the effect of fibre-matrix debonding upon the elastic microbuckling of fibre composites. The model is an adaptation of the Rosen [4] analysis in situations where slip occurs at the fibre-matrix interface; slip begins when the interfacial shear stress attains a critical value. Interfacial shear failure is similar in many respects to shear yielding of the matrix. Steif found that the theoretical fibre breaking strains compared reasonably well with measured failure strains when the kink band was assumed to have the experimentally observed width. His model fails to predict the kink band boundary orientation angle, β .

In summary, although there has been research on the subject for more than twenty years, a unique theoretical model which can predict the compressive strength from the properties of the constituents is still not available.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The compressive failure of unidirectional glass/pp laminates occurs due to fibre microbuckling, regardless of temperature. In the case of specimens tested at approximately 50° C the failure mode changes from in-plane to out-of-plane microbuckling, which initiates at lower applied strains. Failure initiation depends also on material imperfections, such as voids, resin rich regions and fibre misalignment. The progressive decrease in strength with increasing temperature T is associated with the reduction in matrix shear strength properties with increasing T. Thus, in compression the matrix and interface play a key role in providing side support to the fibres and consequently resistance to fibre microbuckling. In currently used composites the strength of glass fibres has been substantially increased while polymeric matrices have changed very little in strength due to demands for high toughness of the composite. As a result, the fibres fail by microbuckling before their compressive strength is reached.

Existing elastic and plastic kinking analyses of microbuckling are able to account for some but not all of the experimental observations. Fibre bending and fibre-matrix interface must be modelled explicitly in order to predict successfully the geometry of the microbuckle band and the compressive strength of the composite.

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Figure 1. Geometry of fibre microbuckling mode [7]
 β =boundary orientation angle;
 ϕ =inclination angle; w =microbuckle width)
 a) in-plane b) out-of-plane microbuckling.

Figure 2. Overall failure mode of glass/pp laminate (buckle length=0.6mm).

Figure 3. Compressive stress-strain response of glass/pp laminate.

Figure 4. Optical microphotograph showing in-plane fibre microbuckling in a glass/pp laminate. ($\beta \approx 25^\circ$ to the horizontal axis, $w = 0.6\text{mm}$)

Figure 5a. Fracture surface of glass/pp laminate after buckling. It shows rows of buckled fibres (26x).

Figure 5b. Higher magnification of (5a) showing that each fibre fails in bending (1700x).

Figure 6. Optical microphotograph showing out-of-plane fibre microbuckling in a glass/pp laminate ($w \approx 1 \text{ mm}$).

Figure 7. Compressive strength of glass/pp laminates as a function of temperature. Theoretical values are obtained from Budiansky's model [8].